

Hydroxyethyl starch and acute kidney injury in high-risk patients undergoing cardiac surgery: A prospective multicenter study

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Abstract

Background

[Hydroxyethyl starch](#) (HES) solutions increase the risk of [acute kidney injury](#) (AKI) in critically ill patients admitted to [intensive care unit](#) (ICU) for medical indications. We conducted a [cohort study](#) to evaluate the renal safety of modern 6% HES solutions in high-risk patients having cardiac surgery.

Method

In this multicentre [prospective cohort study](#), we recruited 261 consecutive patients at high-risk for developing cardiac surgery-associated AKI, based on a Cleveland score ≥ 4 points, from July to December 2017th in 14 hospitals in Spain and the United Kingdom. Multivariable [logistic regression](#) modeling and propensity-score matched-pairs analysis were used to determine the adjusted association between administration of HES and AKI.

Results

Of the cohort, 95 patients (36.4%) received 6% HES 130/0.4 either intraoperatively or postoperatively. Postoperative AKI occurred in 145 patients (55.5%). The unadjusted odds of AKI was significantly higher in the HES group, when compared to those not receiving HES (OR 2.22, 95% CI 1.30–3.80, $p = 0.003$). In multivariable [logistic regression](#) models, modern HES was not associated with significantly increased risk of AKI (adjusted OR 0.84, 95% CI 0.41–1.71, $p = 0.63$). In propensity score match-pairs analysis of 188 patients, the HES group experienced similar adjusted odds of AKI (OR 1.05, CI 95% 0.87–1.27, $p = 0.57$) and [RRT](#) (OR 1.06, CI 95% 0.92–1.22, $p = 0.36$).

Conclusions

The use of modern hydroxyethyl starch 6% HES 130/0.4 was not associated with an increased risk of AKI nor dialysis in this cohort of patients at elevated risk for developing AKI after cardiac surgery.

Keywords

Acute kidney injury; Cardiac surgery; High risk patients; Hydroxyethyl starch; Renal replacement